

The Object Relation Model of Borderline Functioning: A Comprehensive Model Scoping Review

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Abstract

Introduction: Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) reflects a complex personality organization marked by identity diffusion, affective instability, and primitive defenses. Psychoanalytic models—particularly those based on object relations—offer key insights into its psychodynamic foundations. This review aims to synthesize major psychoanalytic models of borderline functioning, identify shared and divergent theoretical elements, and highlight clinical implications for treatment.

Methods: A systematic search was conducted in PsycINFO, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science using terms such as “borderline,” “borderline functioning,” and “object relations.” Included works focused on theoretical models of borderline functioning and psychoanalytic interventions.

Results: The models reviewed converge on core features: unstable object relations, splitting, projective identification, and affect dysregulation. Projective tests, such as the Rorschach, help reveal internal conflict, fragmented self-representations, and defensive patterns in BPD.

Conclusions: Psychoanalytic perspectives, especially object relations theory, provide a rich framework for understanding borderline functioning. An integrated model is proposed to support clinical practice and guide future research.

Keywords: Borderline Personality Disorder; Defense mechanisms; Effective instability; Object relations; Projective identification; Psychoanalysis.

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INTRODUCTION

The understanding of borderline personality organization offers a profound exploration of the unique structure and functioning of this disorder, characterized by fragmented ego organization, unstable object relations, and reliance on primitive defenses [1-3]. Borderline functioning is situated on the continuum between neurotic and psychotic structures, marked primarily by the defense mechanism of "splitting" [4]. This psychological splitting results in polarized and contradictory perceptions of oneself and others, leading to fluctuations between idealization and devaluation and impeding the development of a cohesive self-concept [5,6].

A significant component in borderline pathology is the role of pathological aggression, which disrupts ego cohesion and heightens the tendency toward splitting. This aggression, often originating from early developmental failures and traumatic relational experiences, contributes to an internal environment filled with intense fears of abandonment, pervasive emptiness, and a fragile sense of identity [7,8]. Moreover, deficits in object constancy—the capacity to maintain stable, internalized representations of others—further destabilize the borderline personality, creating a vulnerability to intense but fleeting attachments [9-11].

The aim of this review is to explore and synthesize the existing psychoanalytic models of borderline functioning, with the goal of advancing a comprehensive understanding of its theoretical underpinnings, key mechanisms, and clinical implications. While numerous contributions within psychoanalysis offer valuable insights into borderline functioning—addressing elements such as object relations, defense mechanisms, and ego structure—there remains a challenge in integrating these diverse perspectives into a cohesive, unified model. By mapping and analyzing the range of psychoanalytic approaches, this review seeks to identify both commonalities and distinctions across models, aiming to bridge theoretical gaps and propose an integrative psychoanalytic framework for borderline personality organization. This synthesis will not only clarify theoretical ambiguities but also provide a foundation for clinical applications, offering insights that can inform both future research and psychoanalytic practice.

METHODS

This scoping review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) guidelines [12].

A comprehensive literature search was performed using four major electronic databases: PsycINFO, PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. The search strategy included a combination of free-text terms and standardized subject headings (MeSH terms), aiming to capture both classical and contemporary contributions to the psychoanalytic understanding of borderline functioning. Keywords used in various combinations included: "*borderline*", "*borderline functioning*", "*borderline personality disorder*", "*object relations*", "*psychoanalytic model*", and "*defense mechanisms*". Boolean operators (AND/OR) were used to increase the precision and breadth of the search.

Inclusion criteria were:

- (a) Peer-reviewed journal articles, theoretical reviews, and book chapters discussing psychoanalytic or psychodynamic models of borderline functioning;
- (b) Studies published in English, with no date restriction, to ensure inclusion of historical foundations and contemporary developments;
- (c) Publications that describe or apply psychoanalytic theoretical constructs (e.g., object relations, ego development, primitive defenses) to the understanding or treatment of borderline personality organization.

Exclusion criteria were:

- (i) Empirical studies without a clearly articulated psychoanalytic theoretical framework;
- (ii) Articles focusing exclusively on other psychiatric conditions without reference to borderline functioning;
- (iii) Non-peer-reviewed materials (e.g., conference abstracts, editorials, dissertations).

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts for relevance, followed by full-text assessment of eligible studies. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion. To ensure comprehensive coverage, reference lists of included papers were manually reviewed for additional relevant sources.

Data were extracted and charted to map the following elements:

1. Theoretical components of each model (e.g., object relations, ego structure, affect regulation);
2. Commonalities and divergences between models;
3. Clinical and therapeutic implications;
4. Identified conceptual gaps or areas for future research.

The study selection process is documented in a PRISMA-ScR flow diagram (Figure 1). This review adheres to the methodological and reporting criteria established for scoping reviews, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and clarity.

Figure 1. PRISMA-ScR flow diagram of the study selection process.

RESULTS

The concept of borderline functioning is complex, and several theoretical models have been developed to understand it, each emphasizing different aspects of its nature, development, and treatment. While borderline functioning is most commonly associated with borderline personality disorder (BPD), it represents a broader pattern of psychological organization characterized by identity diffusion, intense emotional instability, and difficulties in relationships. Table 1 presents an overview of some of the main models in the field.

Table 1. Overview of the Object Relation Model addressing Borderline functioning.

No.	Author and year	Main Focus/Findings
1	Nilsson, 1995 [1]	Compares schizophrenia and borderline patients using PORT, based on DSM-III and Kernberg's six structural levels.
2	Bouvet and Cleach, 2011 [2]	Explores the link between dropout rates, relational skills, object relations, and intensity of psychopathology.
3	Holm and Hundevadt, 1981 [3]	Combines Grinker's classification with object relation theory for borderline patients, offering insights into prognosis and psychotherapy.
4	Leichsenring [4]	Compares object relations in borderline and neurotic patients using the Holtzman Inkblot Technique.
5	Diguer L et al, 2012 [5]	Introduces the Object Relations Rating Scale (ORRS) and validates its interrater reliability and scales related to in-session processes.
6	Bürgy, 2007 [6]	Describes despair as an oscillating, affective-cognitive process involving various emotions such as hope, fear, and guilt.
7	Rosenfeld, 1979 [7]	Highlights the analyst's role in understanding object relations and maintaining a therapeutic environment for fragmented mental states.
8	Titelman D et al, 2004 [8]	Explores depressive affect, anxiety, and psychological defenses in suicide attempters using PORT, comparing them to matched controls.
9	Sieswerda S et al, 2005 [9]	Examines dichotomous thinking and splitting in borderline personality disorder through object-relation theories.
10	Bénézech, 1987 [10]	Studies borderline and narcissistic features in criminals driven by passion, focusing on the narcissistic pregenital type of object relation.
11	Combalbert et al, 2006 [11]	Uses the McGill Object Relations Scale to examine object-relation maturity and its relationship to psychopathology.

Analysis of the Object Relations Model

1. The dysphoria and electric overload

The underlying emotional state characterizing individuals with borderline personality disorder (BPD) is a profound dissatisfaction, an eternal unsaturation of unspeakable needs, a continuous search for something else, which manifests in daily life as a tendency towards impulsivity, immediate and unthinking action, and violent and desperate reactivity to potentially aggressive acts, often out of tune with others. There is no void, but rather a constant oscillation between filling and emptying mental spaces, resorting to actions (substance use, reckless sex, transient hysterical mechanisms) that provide temporary relief from the sense of unsaturation and boredom that plagues individuals with BPD. This boredom does not stem from emptiness, but from the anticipation of continuous frustration that the object will inflict [13].

Rossi Monti [14] describes dysphoria as a culmination of various elements such as the inability or rapid decline of symbolization, anger and disappointment, suspicion, nostalgia for something never experienced but whose past existence is intuited, and the desire to reset an internal and external world considered deceptive and violent. None of these behaviors alone seems capable of explaining the distress, but it is their combination that characterizes a sort of confused and unbearable mixture that induces individuals with BPD to discharge these states as quickly as possible: from compulsive smoking to drinking, to taking heavier substances capable of inducing severe and uncontrollable dependencies. The individual with BPD plunges into their psychic states and, once plunged, no longer remembers how they fell into them. This way, they live in an eternal present, now joyful, now distressing, now angry, without a precise reference compass [15]. It is an undifferentiated and confused psychic state, where intense emotions predominate but are so mixed together as to not allow easy recognition, and on the other hand, scattered sensory elements, apparently without a precise location, to orient the overall psychic state and affects [16].

These scattered sensory elements are images or memories or current perceptions that are placed in the psychic field like floating buoys, seeming like objects torn from an all-too-real world, but endowed with a persecutory and almost traumatic capacity. Dysphoria is an emotionally turbulent crucible in which anger, pain, despair, and protest mix, giving it the characteristic of a kind of stable instability. Dysphoria is therefore a restless alarm unaccompanied by a proper understanding of why the individual with BPD feels this way, an unpleasant restlessness, a negativity-tinged restlessness, an expectation without knowing what is expected, a desire for someone to appear and say or do something to pass through this state. The sequence often observed is this: the rupture of a significant relationship, dysphoria (discontent, restlessness, alarm), a sense of unbearable emptiness. A strong need arises to fill this void, with a new and idealized relationship, or with something that serves only to provide pleasure, such as sex, drugs, alcohol, or with reckless acts that restore a sense of vitality and pleasure in place of desertification [17].

Trauma can result in an excess of emotionality which, precisely because it is excessive and lacking the modulated character of tenderness, induces a paralysis of representative functions, also altering memory. With individuals with BPD, there is a sense of being in an impending catastrophe. Their emotional content is not yet a meaning, a defined emotion, but the short circuit between two emotions not yet defined, the explosive spark that triggers a vortex that is made of immediate impacts, instant abrasions, turbulences that determine continuous ripples of consciousness so that time is never calm and moves against a backdrop perceived by the individual with BPD as already stagnant.

Events are experienced overwhelmingly, as exacerbating scenarios that tear apart without the object being able to perform a binding function that soothes their impatience and opens up to assimilative pleasure for a moment of pause and contemplation.

The boundaries (of the Self, of the object, of the relationship) always appear unstable and precarious, or too hostile to ensure life. There is a fear of the threatening emergence of an unrepresentable bottom on which the boundaries struggle to form, or end up breaking reality into two or more parts, instead of integrating different areas. Continuous disorientation follows, a sense of lack of emotional orientation, of emotional thickness of experience, of familiarity with life, and a lack of identity. Dissociation is connected to the difficulty of psychically elaborating a magmatic affectivity, but it also constitutes a kind of guarantee, a protection from an excessive and conflictual awareness of alterity for the limits of the Self [18].

There is a surrender to an undifferentiated emotional state, certainly painful, but nonspecific, which offers relief from the pain of the individual episode but at the cost of a global devaluation of the possible area of relationships. An experience of sorrow and profound irritability, which can be read as a mixture of different emotions, almost all negatively titled, but which constitutes an undifferentiated and indiscriminate reaction to intolerable experiences of pain [13].

These are forms of experience that cannot be well differentiated into psychic or physical states, but are a palpable combination of both, sometimes chaotic and disturbing, other times surprising in their creative and regenerative potential. The individual with BPD tries to defend themselves against intense affects of hatred, anger, against feelings of dispersion and self-loss, against the extinguishing of thought, rather than experiencing and living these disturbing experiences; they try to escape from the experience of chaos and suffering from the absence of libidinal-emotional contact with their own thoughts [18].

Ricoeur [15] speaks of the concept of ipseity, which combines both the element of uniqueness of each subject, and the fact that such uniqueness is projected over time. Instead of feeling their own uniqueness over time as an inner richness to be preserved, individuals with BPD perceive a basic sense of alienation from themselves, of non-coincidence but of fracture between self-image and self-sense. Their inexhaustible search for confirmation, gratifications, or praise, seems to be the desperate desire for some external force to restore a sense of coincidence between self and self-sense.

In his article, Gaddini [16] refers back to Freud [17], who in 1924 spoke of the existence at birth of a protomodel of biological and innate action that will be translated into a parallel psychological model with the development of the Ego, mastery of the neuromuscular apparatus, and the appearance of the reality principle. The innate protomodel of action originally serves the homeostatic function of channeling into the coordinated activity of the muscles involved in suction quantities of energy, whose accumulation causes tension. The tension, which we call hunger, once it exceeds a certain threshold, gives rise to the activity of the suction apparatus. The external object, the breast, towards which the action is directed, comes to meet the action itself. Satiation is the ultimate goal, aimed at reducing painful tension and restoring homeostasis. If undue tension cannot be discharged quickly enough externally, through the coordinated action of suction, it will tend to discharge internally, when the formation of affects, which uses the energy discharged internally.

If undue tension cannot be discharged rapidly enough externally, through coordinated suction action, it will tend to discharge internally, when affect formation, which utilizes the energy discharged internally, is not yet available. The original lack of psychic regulatory mechanisms for internal discharges would explain the infant's enormous vulnerability to homeostatic alterations. The phenomena that constitute pleasure are of a different nature from those that constitute displeasure. Although they have the same quantitative characteristics in terms of tension and discharge, they differ in the quality of energy involved, meaning they are qualitatively different. Pleasure is connected with libidinal energy, while displeasure is connected with aggressive or destructive energy [18]. In 1937, Freud spoke of a compensatory mechanism, an internal mechanism that tends to oppose a massive charge of libidinal energy to the internal discharge of aggressive energy and confronts the homeostatic imbalance through a compensatory operation [19]. The compensatory mechanism

comes into play whenever aggressive tension reaches a certain threshold, and whenever its unavoidable external discharge, which depends solely on the external environment, is delayed, or prevented.

For example, the discharge of the painful tension of hunger, through rhythmically repeated compensatory experiences between the two types of energy, acquires an increasing libidinal capacity to be deferred and increases the capacity to withstand frustration. The hallucinatory image is the first mental manifestation corresponding to the physiological protomodel that tends to counteract the aggressive charges that return internally, in the absence of the object, through the overlap of libidinal charges.

Initially, aggressive energy is much more powerful than libidinal energy, but it is also the most powerful stimulus for the production and process of development and differentiation of libido. Without the possibility of coordinated motor discharge, the initial power of libidinal energy would succumb to that of powerful aggressive energy. Libidinal energy is capable of differentiation, that is, of development in a qualitative sense, and it is the energy destined to acquire psychic qualities.

In fusion processes, aggressiveness, once fused with libido, is involved in its vicissitudes, and made useful for the psychic purposes of the individual. Aggressiveness seems to be the most powerful force behind the differentiation and development of libido. Without fusion processes, the reality principle would not be possible. Aggressiveness makes narcissistic libido objective, drawing it out and channeling it towards objects. This explains why the object relationship is initially characterized by marked destructiveness, and then gradually adapts to reality purposes.

In individuals with BPD, libidinal charges overlap in an undifferentiated mixture with aggressive ones [20]. There is a tension towards something that does not get named. The need itself becomes a continuous search for something else that ends up being an object that cannot be named. The unpredictability of the need charges it with electricity, in which the ability to differentiate whether it is libido or aggressiveness is compromised by its own chaos. The indistinct overload generates a framework of the Self-made of discontinuity holes. A mother who reacts by introducing further anxieties rather than re-elaborated and digestible remediation, fuels the child's further chaotic experience of the maternal object. It is the passage of chaos and discontinuity that disrupts the remediation process. The electric tension that emerges when a need arises is so massive that it leaves fewer possibilities to structure a benevolent relationship with the object. The aggressive quota ends up prevailing over the libidinal one, and the electric overload will result in relationships with persecutory and chaotic objects. The magmatic tension state where aggressiveness and libido circulate intertwined and indistinct triggers terror regarding a need that the individual with BPD does not recognize and cannot recognize. In the absence of a para-excitatory screen, the individual with BPD ends up perceiving only destructiveness within each libidinal quota. The high-tension state where aggressiveness and libido intertwine indistinctly triggers the disabling terror of recognizing its underlying need. This electric tension, in the face of a need, hinders or makes it more difficult to structure a relationship with the object. This does not always happen in individuals with BPD, but only where the tension state is too high to be managed.

1. The relationship with the object

In individuals with Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD), the object is experienced not only as destructive but as destruction itself, represented as emotional turmoil. The primary object is experienced only as a recurring effect within the Self, rather than as a specular phenomenon to be introjected into normal psychic development. When an emotion hints at the presence of such an object, the borderline individual attempts to retrieve the object by transforming a normal sensation into a disturbing experience. The absence or lack of fundamental cumulative projects of maternal desire, which should ensure the representability of the child's needs, creates pure chaos [23].

The borderline individual lives in constant disappointment to protect themselves from the impact that a sudden and real disappointment could have on them or from the difficulty of modulating closeness and distance. Disinterest, dissatisfaction, inadequacy are the most frequent perceptions towards others. Eros and anger are two powerful mental energizers that keep the level of arousal high. Anger is the best energizer, as the more it is practiced, the more it is fueled. The desperate need for excitement is more important than the need for gratification. When anger is no longer sufficient to hold anxiety at bay, promiscuity and dependence emerge as emergency exciters. Desire is condemned forever to be only an ambition and never achieved.

Gaddini [20] speaks of persecutory objects which end up remaining just that, without the transformative possibility of remediation, resulting in a narcissistic wound to the individual's authentic needs for care and nurturing. The internal objects of borderlines are unstable, unreliable, discontinuous, and potentially persecutory: the borderline never knows if they will turn into a benevolent opposite. The need is portrayed as despairing and urgent to the point of becoming distressing and resolved into catastrophe, which, paradoxically, provides reassurance as it is more certain: it is the reassurance of experiencing something known no matter how tragic.

The failure to consolidate a basic trust in the world and in the belief that objects can be transformative within oneself will fuel the accompanying anxiety experience. Catastrophe becomes charged with meaning, while anxiety is linked to emptiness. An object experienced as too persecutory becomes traumatic, preventing it from becoming a transformative object. The need precedes the representation of the object, and the lack of stable and secure access to the objects themselves leads to considering the need itself as the bearer of all evils, which must be defended against by denying the needs themselves. In the phrase "I don't need you," the borderline becomes their own greatest persecutor. Another defensive mechanism is projective identification: the unrepresented and uncommunicable need in words is expelled in a passage from unconscious to conscious without representation. The unrepresentable need becomes a terror driver. The object, not fulfilling its transformative function, becomes a harbinger of electric experience. The chaotic object makes the experience itself chaotic. The need cannot be seen or named; instead, it generates shame and is persecutory.

Projective identification shifts control functions outside the Self; it is not a malevolent control, but it seems that emotional thermostat is assigned to the hands of another, an external, real, and existing figure, perceived not as malevolent and destructive but as inadequate and inadequate. The borderline often presents themselves as eternally misunderstood by the people they know, from whom they are always disappointed. Relationships are imbued with forms of affection in which aspects of adhesive dependence dominate. The partner is continually compared to initial expectations with two possible outcomes: either the delinquent is fired and replaced by another equally delinquent, or one becomes fixated on that disappointing figure that will continue to perform the function of both a projective container and an anger activator, alternating between possibilities ranging from promiscuity to viscosity. In viscous relationships, the goal is not enjoyment but the maintenance of a high level of arousal. The other, transformed into an organ and instrument for satisfying conscious and unconscious needs, ends up being relegated to a partial object, a pawn to be used in a totalitarian manner for one's own needs, whose characteristics are always inadequate, generating frustration and dissatisfaction. The borderline individual seems to apply a parasitic model of relationship: they need to inhabit the mental space of the other, who should take care of their needs completely, and they project into that space to use it as a nest. The borderline expects someone to digest things for them, to do things in their place.

These are partial object relationships, where the other is functionally used for one's own needs and ends up being depleted of their entire function. The other is required to become the one who will be able to solve all needs; they are no longer seen as a person but as a drug-like object for the needs. The other is always attacked and is tolerable only as a

functional object that guarantees total need fulfillment. This results in eternal dissatisfaction and discomfort towards the need that never finds an adequately suitable object or tends to destroy it.

For the borderline individual, thinking about this object or talking about it does not bring the expected relief but a painful circular movement of thoughts that prevents the center from holding onto them. This emotionally intense agitation exists as the place of the primary object through representations of affects, thoughts, and discourses. It seems that the primary object or the mother has been experienced as a destructive movement and ultimately recognizable as a negative transformation of the Self. In this case, the nurturing object becomes the deeply disturbing emotional wake of the other, which includes fear, anger, and destructive hatred awakened in the borderline's Self, a persecutory anxiety that binds the Self and its affective objects in a psychologically indistinguishable struggle of negative forces [23].

The object for the borderline functions as a stimulus with a strong emotional impact, which when evoked activates the sensory. The object is linked to an external but immediately evocative event internally, an outside that is simultaneously inside, indicating the unconscious placement of the primary borderline object. The object that impacts the Self causes alarm, and at the same time, the object is constructed from a precise characteristic of the subject's internal life evoked at that moment. The truth represented by the disaster becomes a temptation for the borderline, who without the catastrophic feels lifeless, and emotionally the absence of catastrophe is felt as destructive to the Self. Agitation is the presence of the object, while tranquility represents the abandonment of the object, a suffering that condemns to a feeling of emptiness. Psychic emptiness becomes part of the presence of the primary object within the Self, which when provoked and then abandoned, is first filled with angry anguish and then empty. Fullness and emptiness not only remind of this object but constitute it. The circular emotional agitation is strangely nourishing and preferable to emptiness. Fueling the emotional storms provided by the other, seeking the catastrophe from which relief is drawn, are ways of transforming the object into a nourishment opportunity, and every traumatic relationship becomes something nourishing. The vortex Self, always on the edge of catastrophe, awaits catastrophic moments to milk them. The search for the sensational binds the Self while fragmenting the Ego [23].

2. Primary object and defense mechanisms

If the maternal function presents excessive gaps or if the environment does not allow the child to retrieve the object, instead offering discontinuity, unpredictability, sudden intrusion, and the unexpected, the child will resort to massive projection mechanisms, distancing sensory experiences, perceptions, or thought sketches from themselves, as if they were not theirs, but always of something else outside of them. Projection would dominate, creating a fragile area of pleasure inside always threatened by an unpredictable and dangerous external. The concepts of internal and external themselves will be precarious: the internal is always fragile and crumbling because projection continuously empties it. The internal flows outward, and the external becomes a projected internal [13].

The caregiving object fails in its primary function of regulating the child's internal states, namely, that modulating function that allows a harmonious transition from the pleasure principle to the reality principle, from the judgment of attribution that includes only dichotomous categories (good/bad, right/wrong, yes/no) to the judgment of existence that involves acquiring the reality of the whole object, existing outside of the Self. Instead, if the caregiving object exposes the child to pervasive discontinuity of experience, making it unfindable, or if it is too frustrating, absent, or unpredictable, the child will resort to massive projection mechanisms aimed at expelling everything that cannot be processed and transformed. The internal and external become poorly defined, the boundary between the two very fluid and unstable, and the internal is fragile and precarious because it is continually emptied by the need to expel the persecutory nature of objects. The persistence of positive experiences allows for the gradual establishment of mechanisms of repression, that is, that kind of mental operation that consists of retaining something of the object in memory, albeit modified by modeling

processes, through modes of investment and divestment, of partial aspects of the object itself. Repression allows for the division between conscious and unconscious, closely connected with that between internal and external.

The lack of continuity of experience and of an object capable of containing and transforming will prevent the gradual establishment of the repression mechanism, understood not only as a defense mechanism but also as a primary function of the mind, that chiasmus between conscious and unconscious, internal and external, responsible for the stability of the boundary and for creating the unconscious.

Melanie Klein [24] takes up the theme of exteriorization and states that the excessive use of projective identification, aimed at freeing the subject from painful experiences and from the bad and angry parts directed against the object, with consequent feelings of guilt and persecution, leads to an impoverishment of the mind and a precarious and unstable situation of identifications. Libido disorders presuppose a disconnection between destructive drives and libido and the prevalence of destructive drives over libido. If the Ego and the introjected objects are felt as shattered, the infant experiences all this as an internal catastrophe, which is extended to the external world and projected onto it [25].

The predominance of projective mechanisms entails excessive instability of the internal world. In order to construct a possible sense of continuity of one's own existence, idealization comes into play, understood as attributing intense value to certain phenomena or elements of psychic life. However, idealization needs a split to maintain itself, and this allows for the establishment of momentary moments of relief and a possible order in the world, which would otherwise be dominated by disorder, created by the multiplicity of projected and unmetabolized objects. Splitting is established as an attempt to save what can be saved, in a world dominated by exteriorization and by a lack of understanding and meaning.

Splitting mechanisms, secondary to excessive projection mechanisms, do not allow for the expected, the deferral of the immediate, the ability to imagine, understood as the ability to establish connections even between very distant mental elements. The borderline thus lives this private madness, of great passions and poor judgments, of an empty internal world and an external world that is poorly understandable, where, however, internal and external are continuously subject to slipping into each other, providing a continuous experience of existential precariousness.

The Ego is continually subject to experiences of perforation and hemorrhage, due to the prevalence of externalizing mechanisms. The object is laden with evil, anger, and persecutory efforts, striving to make itself present through these invasive modalities. The subject is left with only protective isolation, filled with the use of substances that provide ephemeral pleasures and require continuous repetitions, or a love-hate relationship, unstable ambivalence, with an object chosen as relatively stable, or in transitioning from one precarious investment to another, with an underlying sense of boredom because no object truly installs itself within the subject.

- Through projective identification, the other is somehow forced to be as the projecting subject wants it to be, in order for the subject to rid themselves of unwanted and undesired parts.
- The lack of identifications or partial identification through incorporation produces an insatiable and angry object hunger, akin to a sexual relationship, where orgasm leaves a feeling of dissatisfaction.
- The lack of verbal representation leads to reading the unrepressed unconscious as the reservoir of every experience that could not be transformed by the metaphorical power of the other's mind, put into shared words.

The unconscious will be imbued with diffuse, liquid, uncontrollable emotionality, an absorbing discomfort [26] that cannot be spoken but only felt or made to be felt through projective identification, aimed not only at getting rid of something but also at making that something communicable when words are lacking [27]. Splitting is not a primary phenomenon that precedes projection but serves the function of saving what can be saved, of establishing, through idealization, a possible order of the world; as if the relationship with the other were so desperately filled with destructiveness that the only way to try to oppose it was to build a narcissistically idealized object relationship. In a sense, hallucinating a totally good and

eternally present object that finally allows one to be with oneself and with the other in a state of rest, of tranquil trust. However, this strategy is doomed to failure: the split aspects return loaded with the persecutorily intrusive quality that is linked to the mechanism of projective identification. The subject seems condemned to oscillate between loss and intrusion: it can never be completely separate, but it is never stably with. Neither the Ego nor the object is stable: hence the hungry dependence and the exacerbated rejection, the undifferentiated turbulence made up of great passions and poor judgments in a present that devours everything.

Affective states are psychic phenomena that play important unconscious functions. Some are an opportunity to express a conservative object, that is, an internal state of the rejected Self that has been preserved intact in childhood. When someone experiences a certain mood, they become that infantile Self that could not express itself in relation to the parents. Therefore, moods often represent the existential record of breakdown moments between child and parents and partially indicate the arrest of the parent's development, who could not address the child's specific maturation needs correctly. An experience of the child's Self is rejected by parents who fail to function as transformative objects, relegating the Self state to a freeze in a conservative object that can only be represented in moods [28].

An infantile generative introjection occurs when the child internalizes a part of the mother, thus merging it internally with a drive, and when the child reprojects the introject, comparing it with the intrinsic characteristics of the mother, in order to feel a certain harmony with the external world. If the mother is an insufficient self-object, the child must form a kind of alternative self that in most cases will be composed of projected self-states, such as isolation, despair, frustration, and anger.

Whenever we notice that one person forces another to bear an unwanted part of themselves, we speak of projective identification. Extractive introjection is a procedure by which one person invades another's mind and appropriates some elements of their mental life. As a result, the victim of extractive introjection will feel deprived of some parts of the self. For example, a parent who projectively identifies unwanted split elements of their self in the child will burden the child with a very complex and chaotic inner world, and as an adult, the child may become an unintegrated magma of innate self-parts and unwanted parental introjects. There is a dysfunctional introjection of the internal presence of a good object capable of being recalled in moments of absence.

Every extractive introjection is accompanied by the corresponding projective identification. When something is taken away, a void, a gap, remains in place of what has been removed. Despair or a sense of emptiness is deposited here. If one person invades another's psychic territory, they not only deposit an unwanted part of themselves, as in the case of projective identification, but also take something. By putting unwanted parts of themselves into another person, the projector enjoys a limited mental peace, a psychic state that is extracted from the receiver, who now finds themselves in a state of confusion.

During the reunification phase described by Mahler [29], the child who has already separated from the mother returns to her for comfort and protection after experiencing being alone. An empathetic and encouraging attitude from the mother enhances the experience and allows for a more secure and satisfying memory inscription, whereas an intrusive, devaluing, or controlling response can render it disorganized or unreadable or prevent its memorization. Fonagy [30] hypothesized a severe disturbance in communication between mother and child in borderlines, linked to the child's perception of unconscious hostile aspects in the mother. This leads to the inability to share not so much the experience, but the common lived experience of the experience, namely its recategorization afterwards with an emotionally significant figure. A subjective experience of emptiness and loneliness is observed, a hemorrhagic sense of time and life where experiences fail to be deposited but are subject to a continuous flow of loss.

In the field of Self Psychology, Adler [31] talks about the lack of an Object-Self function by the attachment figure. Adler speaks of soothing, which can be translated as softening, mollifying, fluidifying. One aspect of the Object-Self function is given by the modulating and fluidifying activity of the caregiving figure. Soothing, reminiscent of Winnicott's holding [32], is closely related to the mother's ability to have the child tell her about their experiences in the specific communicative form of their age, and not just to share them materially with him as they occur. Adler talks about the difficulty of mechanisms of introjection of the good object, so the borderline lives in a continuous state of emotional deprivation, which is compensated for by seeking, sometimes incongruous, behaviors with a revitalizing function.

A specific mode of object relationship is observed, where the borderline seems to be frightened and insecure every time they experience excessive closeness to the desired object. The object is felt as unreliable, insidious, unpredictable, and unable to ensure a harmonious and constant emotional flow. The way of perceiving every object as potentially traumatic is accompanied by a fantasy sensation of potentially opposite character. The borderline tends, impulsively and uncontrollably, to establish powerful emotional bonds, investing the object with idealizing fantasies and loading it with expectations, often unrealistic, of complete satisfaction of personal and total emotional needs. This results in sudden approaches, intensely felt but subjectively perceived as inevitable candidates for frustration, and withdrawals, activated to prove to oneself a non-existent independence and capacity for self-sustainment.

A devitalizing mode of relationship by the object itself is observed. In these cases, the trauma of the object seems to be related to the dampening effect on the child's affects and enthusiasms, which the object would exercise, not through overt physical or psychological attacks, but through an active coldness, a kind of unspoken hostility toward the child's psychic life. These parents behave as if the child's psychic life were experienced by them as a chaotic and uncontrollable force, which therefore needs to be dampened to be brought back within tolerable limits.

The borderline constantly seeks acute pleasure in an orgasmic mode of pleasure to keep the distressing tendency to impoverish the internal world at bay and to replace the sensation of not holding within oneself a significant, modulating, and protective object.

This mode of response to the traumatic object has the positive consequence of avoiding a depressive flood and existential emptiness but has the negative consequence of impoverishing the subjective thickness of lived experience, with a profound distortion of the sense of time and memory, which become precipitous and persecutory.

The activation of a specific emotion does not acquire the character of an awareness of the presence of something defined within oneself, but is experienced as a specific activation, a generalized restlessness, a push to act, a need for closer and more engaging contacts with loved ones. The only recognized and often predominant, invasive, and omnipresent affect is anger. The failure to recognize affective states may be related to a traumatic environment, in which the child's emotional state was not recognized by the caregiving figure, and therefore not shared and returned in a liveable and bearable form [33]. Instead of recognizable affective states, intense emotional waves are active, experienced more as bodily disturbances, chaotic sensations of overwhelm. The affective-perceptual texture of reality is somehow modified by the absence of a stable affective substrate on which to place perception itself.

Being able to recognize and express affective states through symbols allows the constitution of a mental space, where such symbols can be connected, maintained, or modified. The excessive unmodified power of affective states or a lacking capacity for shared verbalization leaves the affective world chaotic, indiscriminate, and pervasive, without a mental container that performs reflexivity operations [34]. It seems to be what happens to borderlines in whom the expression of an affect can be subjected to distortion, expulsion, denial, with effects of shame and anger, and even of loss of recognizability of that affect itself. The verbal phase will therefore develop against the background of a powerful but confused affective world, and will not be able to bring order, but will instead add a sense of distance and incompatibility

between different parts of the mind. Their subjective experience is a mass of intense affects, but little distinct from each other, pressing like an oppressive, indistinct, and heavy effect, while the mental area, capable of offering this chaotic mass order and recognizability, is precarious and discontinuous. This prefigures the difficulty of acquiring a sense of constancy of internal objects, whose presence continuity within subjective experience is questioned. Objects do not merge with affects and remain transient and precarious. An object cannot be stably represented without knowing what we feel for it.

The object world assumes stability and constancy only if the affective world is readable and discriminable; otherwise, the disorder and indecipherability of affects result in the non-installation of internal objects in our mental world.

The borderline tends to experience the need to always seek new objects because the existing ones are never satisfying or to ask the object for constantly new demonstrations of effectiveness, presence, and availability. Very often, the future borderline child has felt that the expression of an emotion did not culminate in a reassuring sharing, but rather, it caused significant distortions or receptions of contrast and disrespect outside of him. Emotional expression often led to a painful sensation of losing the emotion itself. The various islands, not connected to each other, in which the borderline frantically moves, may represent the outcome of an attempt at vitalization, using various and different expedients to avoid the sense of their own internal chaos, experienced as too full which becomes an emptiness [35].

Each object is confused, chaotic, and hides unpredictable pitfalls within itself. The lack of constancy of internal objects makes separations devastating and the memory of the conquest of positive experiences precarious. The relationship with time is disturbed and irregular: the borderline does not experience the sensation of time as an ordered flow, but as a series of partial episodes, each of which has its own space. This results in a sense of time characterized by anxieties of loss of experience and a hemorrhagic sense of self. Instead of flowing, there is an immobile sensation of confused agitation without direction, or boredom and emptiness. The borderline feels on one hand the desperate need for an intensely affective relationship for their sense of time to acquire a mode of flow that is more orderly and bearable. On the other hand, the intense persecutoriness of internal objects and the experiences of inconsistency or unsaturation make every approach felt as intrusive or lacerating. Things go as if the numerous traumatic experiences in the early stages of life left a void of sufficiently organizing identifications. In the absence of these organizing identifications, the subject lives in a condition of friability, of continuous, possible crumbling. What is feared above all is one's own pain as an experience of loss and separation. The alternative to thoughtless discharge directed outward is the proposal of possible identifications that modify the experience of friability and consumption. But the struggle is long, because possible identifications come and go and, with each frustration, can be lost as soon as they are gained. The following resumes the conceptual model of Borderline personality functioning, by including the main theoretical point addressed.

3. Borderline manifestations in projectives

Projective tests are invaluable in the psychoanalytic exploration of areas that are challenging to articulate or in identifying internal conflicts and unconscious defense mechanisms that the individual might not be fully aware of [36-38]. This makes these tools particularly apt for the psychotherapeutic treatment of personality disorders, such as borderline personality disorder, where patients often struggle to verbally express their complex internal experiences.

Within the context of borderline functioning, the responses elicited by projective tests can uncover specific and revealing patterns. Individuals with borderline traits frequently exhibit responses that reflect significant emotional instability and an impaired capacity to regulate affect. Their interpretations of Rorschach inkblots, for example, may include elements of magical thinking and distorted perceptions, along with a tendency to perceive images as chaotic or threatening. These interpretations mirror their internal experiences of intense emotional turbulence and conflict. Typically, these individuals exhibit a pronounced impulsivity in their responses, characterized by dramatic swings between

idealization and devaluation. This oscillation may be seen as a reflection of their difficulties in interpersonal relationships and in maintaining a coherent sense of self [39].

A study by Mihura [40] examined the response characteristics in subjects with borderline personality disorder using the Rorschach test. The findings highlighted a high frequency of responses indicating concrete thinking, difficulties in impulse control, and a tendency to perceive the world in terms of threat or danger. Often, these individuals interpret the inkblots in ways that reveal an internal struggle with feelings of emptiness or anger.

Another significant aspect is the use of primitive defense mechanisms, such as splitting [41]. In the Rorschach test, this may manifest through responses that categorically divide the images into 'good' or 'bad' without any intermediate nuances. This reflects the tendency of individuals with borderline traits to view the world and relationships in starkly dichotomous terms, oscillating between extremes of idealization and devaluation [42].

Regarding specific interpretations, subjects with borderline traits may provide responses that include distorted or incomplete human figures, which could symbolize their perception of themselves and others as incomplete or damaged. A study by Genovese et al. [43] suggests that such responses are frequent in individuals with borderline personality disorder and can be interpreted as a sign of identification with damaged aspects of their self-image.

Table 2. A comprehensive model of Borderline functioning in a psychodynamic perspective.

Dimensions	Description
Core experience of need and catastrophe	Individuals with borderline functioning experience intense and often indistinguishable needs, leading to catastrophic living where needs are perceived as eternally unfulfillable and relationships as inherently unreliable and transient.
Relational dynamics	<p>Partial Object Relations: Relationships are characterized by partial object relations, where others are not seen as whole beings but rather as objects to fulfill intense, unnamable needs.</p> <p>Persecutory Object Relations: There is a predominant experience of others as persecutory and chaotic, contributing to a destabilizing effect on the individual's sense of self and world.</p> <p>Idealization and Devaluation: A pattern of idealizing and then devaluing others, driven by the unmet and intense needs, further complicates relational dynamics.</p>
Defense mechanisms and psychic States	<p>Projective Identification: This mechanism is frequently employed, where unbearable aspects of the self are projected onto others, leading to a distorted perception of relationships and intensifying feelings of persecution.</p> <p>Dissociation: To manage overwhelming affect and relational turmoil, dissociation serves as both a protective and destabilizing mechanism, contributing to a fragmented sense of self.</p> <p>Disforia: A profound state of unease and dissatisfaction marks the borderline experience, characterized by a mix of intense, unregulated emotions that are hard to symbolize or articulate meaningfully.</p>
Trauma and Identity fragmentation	Impact of Trauma: Early relational traumas, often involving caregivers, significantly influence the development of borderline functioning, perpetuating cycles of need and catastrophe.

	<i>Identity and Self-Perception:</i> The borderline individual struggles with a cohesive sense of self, often feeling fragmented, lost, and perpetually on the verge of psychological collapse.
Temporal and emotional dysregulation	<i>Dysregulated Temporal Experience:</i> Time is experienced as disjointed and chaotic, with a difficulty in integrating past, present, and future into a coherent narrative. <i>Emotional Intensity and Instability:</i> Emotional experiences are intense, often indistinct, and overwhelming, with a pronounced difficulty in identifying, regulating, and expressing emotions in a healthy way.
Quest for healing and transformation	Despite the turbulent and often painful psychological landscape, there exists a continuous search for healing, stability, and transformation. This search is marked by the challenging task of navigating intense needs, fluctuating emotions, and complex relational dynamics.

CONCLUSIONS

How can the borderline recognize and fulfill the need for self-care if they have never experienced maternal reverie? How can the borderline access their various needs without being overwhelmed? How to do so without succumbing to a catastrophic experience that does not allow for transformative opportunities for introjected objects, always so ephemeral and shaky?

Those who live along the narrow and dangerous border, a non-space, suffer from a lack of nourishment and support from this ocean: in its place, there is an endless territory occupied not by reclamation, determined by a creative and yet real illusion, but by an expectation waiting to be deciphered, unexplored, on the borders between life and death, between good and evil on an archaic level [18]. On the edge of this unfathomable abyss, one always lives on the brink of psychological collapse, of a breakdown [44-46].

An important clue for accepting the presence of an identification is evocative capacity [28]. The evocation of a distant object brings forth a relationship and modifies the sense of emptiness. It is easy to lose oneself, it is much more painful to reclaim one's self, that is, the sense of one's existence and its continuity over time. The positive and gratifying element of this painful process is the acquisition of affectionate emotions towards oneself and others [15], which compensate for the effort and loss of that sense of false autonomy and proud independence that has always accompanied the borderline. The satisfaction is that pain is better than discomfort because it has content and opens up to others, while discomfort only pushes for its quick, albeit precarious, elimination [47-49].

Needs remain inexhaustible throughout life and can be either an eternal transformative movement or, as in the case of borderlines, an eternal persecution.

It is necessary to help the borderline patient in this process of evocation and encourage them to seek possible and reclaimable pleasures, instead of a self-sufficient and greedy pride or the obligatory recourse to the destructiveness intrinsic to every object relationship [50,51]. Analysis replaces the discharge from ephemeral relief and provokes a pleasure that derives from naming things and can be considered as the reacquisition of one's instinctual capacities, as a non-catastrophic recognition of one's needs, in a context that is not chaotic and violent, but subjective and responsible.

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References

1. Nilsson A. Differentiation between patients with schizophrenia and borderline disorders in the Percept-genetic Object-Relation Test, PORT. *Br J Med Psychol.* 1995 Dec;68(Pt 4):287-309. doi: 10.1111/j.2044-8341.1995.tb01837.x.
2. Bouvet C, Cleach C. [Early dropout patients in psychiatric psychosocial rehabilitation treatment and their bindings with relational skills, object relation and intensity of psychopathology]. *Encephale.* 2011 May;37 Suppl 1 . doi: 10.1016/j.encep.2010.03.008.
3. Holm K, Hundevadt E. Borderline states: prognosis and psychotherapy. *Br J Med Psychol.* 1981 Dec;54(Pt 4):335-40. doi: 10.1111/j.2044-8341.1981.tb02571.x.
4. Leichsenring F. [Aspects of object relations in borderline and neurotic patients: an empirical study using the Holtzman Inkblot technique]. *Psychother Psychosom Med Psychol.* 1989 Dec;39(12):463-70. PMID: 2616714.
5. Diguier L, Gamache D, Laverdière O. Development and initial validity of the Object Relations Rating Scale. *Psychother Res.* 2012;22(4):402-16. doi: 10.1080/10503307.2012.662606.
6. Bürgy M. [A introduction to despair as a psychopathological phenomenon]. *Nervenarzt.* 2007 May;78(5):521-2, 524-7, 529. doi: 10.1007/s00115-006-2057-3.
7. Rosenfeld H. Some therapeutic factors in psychoanalysis. *Int J Psychoanal Psychother.* 1978-1979;7:152-64. PMID: 738807.
8. Titelman D, Nilsson A, Estari J, Wasserman D. Depression, anxiety, and psychological defense in attempted suicide: a pilot study using PORT. *Arch Suicide Res.* 2004;8(3):239-49. doi: 10.1080/13811110490436855.
9. Sieswerda S, Arntz A, Wolfis M. Evaluations of emotional noninterpersonal situations by patients with borderline personality disorder. *J Behav Ther Exp Psychiatry.* 2005 Sep;36(3):209-25. doi: 10.1016/j.jbtep.2005.05.004.
10. Bénézech M. [Object loss in criminologic psychiatry or passion according to Werther]. *Ann Med Psychol (Paris).* 1987 Apr;145(4):329-39. PMID: 3314619.
11. Combalbert N, Vautier S, Bourdet-Loubère S. [Preliminary reports from a psychometric fixation-regression study using the McGill Object Relations Scale]. *Encephale.* 2006 Mar-Apr;32(2 Pt 1):238-43. doi: 10.1016/s0013-7006(06)76150-4.
12. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Annals of internal medicine.* 2018 Oct 2;169(7):467-473.
13. Correale A. Disfarsi di Sé. Angoscia borderline e uso di sostanze [Internet]. 2013 [cited 2024 jan 14]. Available from: <http://www.psiche-spi.it>
14. Racalbutto A. Vivendo lungo il border. *Riv Psicoanal.* 2001;47:29-49.
15. Ricoeur P. Il sé come un altro. Milano: Jaca Book; 1992.
16. Gaddini E. Aggressività e principio di piacere. Verso una teoria psicoanalitica dell'aggressività. *Riv Psicoanal.* 1972;18:139-153.
17. Freud S. The economic problem of Masochism. In: Standard Edition. Vol. 19. London: Hogarth; 1961.
18. Freud S. Lettera a Marie Bonaparte, 27 maggio 1937.
19. Bollas C. Il mistero delle cose. Milano: Raffaello Cortina; 2001.

20. Klein M. Scritti. Torino: Bollati Boringhieri; 1978.
21. Klein M. Note su alcuni meccanismi schizoidi. In: Scritti, 1921-1958. Torino: Bollati Boringhieri; 1978.
22. Green A. Psicoanalisi degli stati limite. La follia privata. Milano: Raffaello Cortina; 2001.
23. Bion WR. Il cambiamento catastrofico. Torino: Loescher; 1987.
24. Bollas C. L'ombra dell'Oggetto. Roma: Borla; 1989.
25. Mahler M, Pine F, Bergman FA. La nascita psicologica del bambino. Torino: Boringhieri; 1978.
26. Fonagy P. The roles of mental representations and mental processes in therapeutic action. *Psychoanal Study Child*. 1993;48:9-47.
27. Adler G. Borderline psychopathology and its treatment. New York: J. Aronson; 1985.
28. Winnicott DC. Sviluppo affettivo e ambiente. Roma: Armando; 1970.
29. Lichtenberg YD, Lachmann FM, Fossahage J. Self and motivational systems: toward a theory of technique. Hillsdale, NJ: The Analytic Press; 1992.
30. Bion WR. Apprendere dall'esperienza. Roma: Armando; 1972.
31. Correale A. Memoria e sensorialità nel disturbo borderline. *Psiche*. 1995;III(2-3):137-149.
32. Schiller D, Alessandra NC, Alia-Klein N, Becker S, Cromwell HC, Dolcos F, Eslinger PJ, Frewen P, Kemp AH, Pace-Schott EF, Raber J. The human affectome. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*. 2024 Mar 1;158:105450.
33. Alia-Klein N, Gan G, Gilam G, Bezek J, Bruno A, Denson TF, Hendler T, Lowe L, Mariotti V, Muscatello MR, Palumbo S. The feeling of anger: From brain networks to linguistic expressions. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*. 2020 Jan 1;108:480-97.
34. Settineri S, Le Donne M, Dritto IP, Rizzo A, Mento C. The Rorschach in gynecological suffering: representations and complexes of the VI table. *Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 2015 Sep 5;3(2).
35. Dritto IP, Tummineri S, Moscuzza V, Di Perri CM, Rizzo A, Liotta M, Merlo EM, Ciccirelli C. Type D Personality in infarcted patients a study with the Rorschach projective technique. *Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 2015 Dec 29;3(3).
36. Mento C, Galletti F, Galletti B, Longo P, Bitto E, Rizzo A, Settineri S. Representation, Projection and Cochlear Implant: a single case study. *Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 2014 Jun 12;2(1).
37. Baity MR, Blais MA, Hilsenroth MJ, Fowler JC, Padawer JR. Self-mutilation, severity of borderline psychopathology, and the Rorschach. *Bulletin of the Menninger Clinic*. 2009 Oct;73(3):203-25.
38. Mihura JL. Rorschach assessment of borderline personality disorder. In *Rorschach assessment of the personality disorders 2006 Apr 21* (pp. 177-209). Routledge.
39. Settineri S, Rizzo A. Explorative pathways in projective clinics: essays and clinical researches. *Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 2015; 3 (1).
40. Faraji H, Muhtar NU, Tezcan AE. Determination Emotion Regulation Difficulties in Borderline Personality Disorder with Objective and Projective Tests. *Current Approaches in Psychiatry/Psikiyatride Guncel Yaklasimlar*. 2023 Oct 2;15.
41. Genovese G, Ciccirelli C, Rizzo A, Crucitti M. Perceptual derailment and confabulation in the Rorschach projective technique: A clinical report. *Mediterranean Journal of Clinical Psychology*. 2015 Dec 29;3(3).
42. Mento C, Rizzo A, Alfa R, Carlotta V, Lipari E, Bruno A, Cedro C, Pandolfo G, Muscatello MR, Zoccali RA. The role of basic symptoms and aberrant salience in borderline personality disorder. *Journal of Clinical & Developmental Psychology*. 2020 Feb 1;2(1).
43. Bruno A, Mattei A, Arnone F, Barbieri A, Basile V, Cedro C, Celebre L, Mento C, Rizzo A, Silvestri MC, Muscatello MR. Lifetime psychiatric comorbidity and diagnostic trajectories in an Italian psychiatric sample. *Clinical Neuropsychiatry*. 2020 Oct;17(5):263.
44. Muscatello MR, Rizzo A, Celebre L, Mento C, Pandolfo G, Cedro C, Battaglia F, Zoccali RA, Bruno A. The wounds of childhood: Early trauma subtypes, salience and hyperarousal in a sample of adult psychiatric patients. *International journal of social psychiatry*. 2020 Feb;66(1):3-9.
45. Bruno A, Rizzo A, Muscatello MR, Celebre L, Silvestri MC, Zoccali RA, Mento C. Hyperarousal scale: Italian cultural validation, age

- and gender differences in a nonclinical population. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2020 Feb;17(4):1176.
46. Rizzo A, Della Villa L, Crisi A. Can the Problematic Internet Use evolve in a pre-psychotic state? A single case study with the Wartegg. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 2015 Oct 1;51:532-8.
47. Rizzo A, La Rosa VL, Commodari E, Alparone D, Crescenzo P, Yıldırım M, Chirico F. Wanna bet? Investigating the factors related to adolescent and young adult gambling. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*. 2023 Oct 8;13(10):2202-13.
48. Siligato E, Iuele G, Barbera M, Bruno F, Tordonato G, Mautone A, Rizzo A. Freezing Effect and Bystander Effect: Overlaps and Differences. *Psych*. 2024 Feb 26;6(1):273-87.
49. Nicita E, Bruno F, Rizzo A. *Oltre lo Stigma verso la Psicoterapia. Teorie, ricerche, soluzioni*. Barnes & Noble press; 2023. ISBN 9798855618440.
50. Rizzo A., Gatto E., Calandi L., Alfa R. *Embodied Online Therapy*. Nova Science Publishers; 2024. ISBN: 9798891135376. DOI: 10.52305/TCJD121
51. Giampà A. "Embodied Online Therapy": The efficacy of somatic and psychological treatment delivered digitally. *Adv Med Psych Public Health*. July 2024;1(3):164-169. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10901015

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